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The Perception of Good Health in Europe

Between 2010 and 2021 it grew on average of 4.24% for the countries considered

The Eurostat calculates the value of the perception of the good health of the population. The indicator takes into consideration the population having an age equal to or over 16 years of age. The condition of health is placed on a staircase ranging from "very good" or "very bad". The indicator considers the percentage of the population that declares a "good" or "very good" health. The data relating to perceived health are a predictor of the consumption of health care and the mortality of people in the future.

Ranking of European countries for the value of good health perceived in 2021. Switzerland is in the first place for the value of good health perceived in 2021 with an amount of 81.8%, followed by Ireland with an amount of 81.2% and by the Greece with a value of 78.3%. In the middle of the standings there are Spain with an amount of 71.2%, followed by Finland with an amount of 70.1%, and Slovenia with an amount of 69.1%. Portugal closes the ranking with an amount of 50.2%, followed by Latvia with an amount of 49.8% and Lithuania with an amount of 47.9%. On average in 2021 the value of good health perceived in the countries analyzed is equal to an amount of 68.5%.

Ranking of European countries for the value of the percentage variation of good health perceived between 2010 and 2021. Croatia is in the first place for the value of the percentage variation of the perception of good health with a variation equal to an amount of 30.29% equal to an amount of 14.6 units, followed by Hungary with an amount of 17.6% equal to an amount of 9.7 units and Slovenia with an amount of 15.75% equal to an amount of 9.4 units. In the middle of the standings there are Greece with an amount of 3.43% equal to an amount of 2.6 units, followed by Finland with an amount of 2.34% equal to an amount of 1.6 units and from Portugal with an amount of 1.83% equal to an amount of 0.9 units. Denmark closes the ranking with a variation equal to an amount of -5.9% equal to an amount of -4.2 units, followed by the Netherlands with an amount of -6.03% equal to an amount of -4, 7 units, and Sweden with an amount of -7.65% equal to an amount of -6 units. On average, the value of healthy perception is growth for the countries considered by 4.24% equal to an amount of 2.3 units between 2010 and 2021.

Clusterization with K-means algorithm optimized with the silhouette coefficient. Below is a clusterization with the K-means algorithm optimized with the silhouette coefficient. Two clusters are identified as indicated below or:

- Cluster 1: Belgium, Spain, Netherlands, Greece, Malta, Denmark, Luxembourg, Cyprus, Sweden, Austria, Romania, Switzerland, Finland, Ireland, Italy, France, Bulgaria, Germany, Slovenia;
- Cluster 2: Portugal, Latvia, Estonia, Lithuania, Croatia, Hungary, Poland, Czech Republic.

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From the median point of view, it appears that the value of the 1-C1 cluster is equal to 72.8 units while the value of the 2-C2 cluster is equal to an amount of 60.55. From a geographical point of view, it appears that the value of Eastern Europe's countries is lower, considering the median, of about 12.3 points compared to the corresponding value of the west Europe.

Network analysis with the Euclidean distance. A Network Analysis is presented below with the Euclidean distance. Two structures are identified with complex networks and a simplified network structure.

There is the following complex network structure as indicated below or:

- Spain has a connection with Belgium for an amount of 0.38 units;
- Belgium has a connection with Spain and the Netherlands for an amount of 0.51 units;
- The Netherlands has a connection with Belgium for an amount of 0.51 units and with Sweden for an amount of 0.45 units;
- Sweden has a connection with the Netherlands for an amount of 0.45 units.
- There is also a complex network structure as indicated below or:
- Luxembourg has a connection with Denmark for an amount of 0.48 units;
- Denmark has a connection with Luxembourg for an amount of 0.48 units and with Austria for an amount of 0.48 units;
- Austria has a connection with Denmark for an amount of 0.48 units and with Romania for an amount of 0.19 units;
- Romania has a connection with Austria for an amount of 0.19 units and with Finland with an amount of 0.43 units;
- Finland has a connection with Romania for an amount of 0.43 units and with France for an amount of 0.47 units;
- France has a connection with Finland for an amount of 0.47 units and with Bulgaria for an amount of 0.3 units;
- Bulgaria has a connection with France for an amount of 0.3 units and with Germany for an amount of 0.37 units;
- Germany has a connection with Bulgaria for an amount of 0.37 units.

There is also a simplified network structure as indicated below or:

- Hungary and Poland have a connection for an amount of 0.36 units.

Conclusions. The value of the state of good health perceived has increased by 4% on average between 2010 and 2021 in the European countries considered. However, there are countries in which the value of perceived health decreased between 2010 and 2021 or Spain, Ireland, Germany, Lithuania, Denmark, the Netherlands, and Sweden. In general, the value of health perceived in Eastern Europe tends to be lower than the value of health perceived in the Europe of the West. The perception of good health anticipates the demand for health services by the population. If the value of perceived health worsens, the population is likely to increase the demand for health services. On the contrary, if the value of perceived health improves, it is likely that there is a reduction in the demand for health services. This indication could also be used at regional and urban level to estimate the progress of the future demand of health services and organize the offer through the health network, and avoid congestion, in the efficiency of the health economy of public and private organizations.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

Buona Salute Percepita nel 2021. Fonte: Eurostat

Clusterizzazione C1>C2

